

Social-Psychological and Spiritual-Educational Factors of a Healthy Lifestyle in Educating a Perfect Generation

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Abstract:

In the article, socio-psychological and spiritual-educational factors of the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle are psychologically analyzed. Also, the article presents psychological recommendations for forming young people's ideas about a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: Healthy lifestyle, health, imagination, youth spirituality, physically healthy, mentally mature, moral requirements and standards, social environment, standard of living.

Raising a perfect generation should not only be physically healthy, but also developed in the spirit of oriental morals and universal ideas. First of all, a person should be healthy, and for this, it is necessary to form concepts and ideas about a healthy lifestyle [1]. That's why raising everyone to appreciate their health from a young age is an integral part of the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle .

A healthy lifestyle is the most important problem facing humanity , that is, it is a socially reasonable lifestyle that helps the population to work, rest and socialize, to form a physically healthy, mentally mature, and morally healthy new generation [2].

A healthy lifestyle is related to people's quality of life, health, mood, aspirations, confidence , the degree to which daily changes meet the needs of our people, the level of socio-economic and spiritual development of the society, and most importantly, the measures that ensure the high efficiency of the education of the young generation.

A healthy lifestyle is determined by increasing the level of well-being of the population, improving health care and household services, bringing the demographic processes to an acceptable state, increasing the spiritual culture, health, moral education of the family, and their activity in social work [3]. A healthy lifestyle includes such complex factors as work, living and recreation, interpersonal culture, environmental culture, keeping one's body in a physiologically optimal state, as well as caring for the health of others.

Proper organization of free time is one of the important conditions for a healthy lifestyle in raising a mature generation. It is appropriate for children, especially teenagers, to spend their free time with their parents at the cinema, parks or various amusement parks. Because any child left unsupervised will definitely learn harmful habits. Especially among teenagers aged 11-15 years, interest in trying them increases after stories about smoking tobacco, tasting alcohol, and "getting high" on drugs. In addition, it is no secret that today's rapid growth of modern information technologies, i.e., computers, mobile phones, and the Internet, have a negative impact on young people.

It is known that there is a specific sphere of influence between the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle in young people and the social environment. This mechanism of interaction appears in our eyes in three different forms.

assigns a person a certain direction that does not correspond to social norms, in particular, roles for performing non-human tasks. Thirdly, inhuman guidance and distribution of roles causes the young people to gradually deform in relation to the demands and standards of the social environment. This deformation causes specific negative changes in a person's consciousness. Therefore, most young people who do not have ideas about a healthy lifestyle are at the stage of deformation in relation to the social environment.

According to our observations, the majority of young people who do not have ideas about a healthy lifestyle are those who do not participate in socially useful activities, who do not read newspapers, magazines or fiction. Therefore, the formation of ideas and concepts about a healthy lifestyle in young people will help them to engage in science, socially useful activities, and most importantly, the formation of a positive attitude towards a healthy lifestyle.

In addition, engaging in socially useful activities, reading books, newspapers, and going to theaters causes the emergence of socially useful positive positions and attitudes in young people. On the contrary, young people there is an opportunity to form negative positions and assumptions in his mind. Young people with such views and charters have poorly developed ideas and skills to follow a healthy lifestyle.

Our observations show that young people who do not study anywhere, do not work, form the core of young people who do not have ideas about a healthy lifestyle. The fact that such people say regretful and regretful things like "I got into this situation due to my negligence" and "I couldn't prevent it at the time" only after they have some kind of disease, indicates that young people do not have enough ideas about a healthy lifestyle.

It is known from the information about young people who do not have ideas about a healthy lifestyle that they always achieve low levels during their activities. For example, the habit of studying poorly at school, breaking general rules and regulations at work, not following moral requirements and standards, constantly having conflicts and disagreements with adults and peers, etc. Also, in such cases, slowness of mental development and lack of strong interest in certain activities is also observed.

The social environment of young people who do not have ideas about a healthy lifestyle is also distinguished by the fact that they have a narrow worldview, a wide range of conflicting situations, a firm life position, a positive outlook on the future, lack of goals and aspirations, and a number of

similar aspects. The state of existence of ideas about a healthy lifestyle is among young people has a positive effect on the formation of a healthy lifestyle .

According to our observations, the type of person and the level of his spiritual and moral maturity have a unique place in the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle. Poor spiritual and moral development and specific characteristics of the personality type (changeable character, excitability, instability, emotionality, subordination, lack of courage, etc.) in young people may be the cause of neglect of a healthy lifestyle .

Probability scheme of the formation of perceptions about a healthy lifestyle

If we analyze this situation from a psychological point of view, the lack of spiritual and moral development of a person, lack of enlightenment can lead to sharp and strong experience of various conflict situations in life , and due to his lack of enlightenment , there may be cases of non-observance of a healthy lifestyle .

Also, the slow development of moral and moral qualities in the personality of young people can cause inattention and lack of interest in their health .

Factors related to family education in the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle in young people" developed by us in order to study the influence of spiritual and educational factors on the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle of young people in the family .

According to the results of our research, perceptions of healthy lifestyle among young people " Weakening of attention to the education of children in the country and failure to control their activities" (24.30%) appears as one of the main factors in the formation of

our observations , in recent years, due to various reasons, in particular , the reforms taking place in our country, experiencing market relations, people's lack of ability to overcome difficulties and look at the future in a new way, etc. and it leads parents to communicate less with their children . Therefore, in the following years in our country, there is an increasing need for various activities, (sports, vocational) clubs, which deal with children's growth and education outside the family.

secondary education" is one of the factors related to family education, which causes the formation of ideas about an unhealthy lifestyle in young people (8.21%) . In this way of education, education is carried out on the basis of extreme strictness, authoritarianism, disregarding the opinions and views of children. Today, life itself shows that it is wrong to raise children in this way. Because today's youth are intellectually mature, have their own views, and strive for independent thinking. We must not forget that counting with such young people, listening to their opinions and opinions, giving advice in the right places will give good results.

The use of methods such as rudeness, indifference, insults, threats and physical punishment in family upbringing often lead to children and teenagers running away from home, doing some work, wandering the streets and staying overnight somewhere because they are afraid of their parents . Such children face the process of social and psychological disadaptation in relation to the family environment.

It is known that drastic psychophysiological changes occur during adolescence, which is considered the age of puberty (12-14 years old). These changes often affect the adolescent's psyche. This is the reason for the emergence of moodiness, capriciousness, capriciousness, impressionability in a teenager. Such changes that appeared in the mental world of a teenager become a norm with the passage of adulthood. Therefore, during puberty, it is appropriate for parents to pay special attention to the upbringing of adolescents, to take into account the psychophysiological changes that are taking place in them. But sometimes, the age and individual-psychological characteristics of children are not taken into account in family education, which causes them to enter wrong and bad ways. Therefore, if parents work in family upbringing, interpersonal relations with their children, taking into account the personality and age characteristics of young people, it is possible to achieve a high level of effectiveness of family upbringing.

In youth Among the factors related to family education that influence the origin of unhealthy lifestyle, the situation of "insufficient knowledge of children's education among parents" is clearly visible (8.42%).

The lack of theoretical and practical knowledge and skills of children's education in parents causes defects in family education.

In a family, parents often try to discipline their children by severely punishing them, banning them, and keeping them out of the house if they do something bad. If their child does something they like, they praise and reward him excessively. They do not realize which of the methods they are using are correct and which are incorrect. They think that this is how education is given by themselves. As a result, they unknowingly have a negative impact on children's education.

1 – table "factors related to family education in the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle in young people" (N-450)

No	Factors of formation of healthy lifestyle psychology in young people depending on family upbringing	I first adolescence (11 -12) age	Adolescence (13 -15) age	Childhood (16-18) age	Average performance gych
1	Loss of attention to the upbringing of children in the family and failure to control their activities	22.20	23.06	25, 24	24.30
2	Inadequate knowledge of parents on raising children	7, 66	9.26	7, 68	8.42
3	Use of ineffective, outdated methods in family upbringing	9.24	8.33	6.32	8.21
4	Not using our national values in family upbringing	6.42	7.28	8.10	7.42
5	Failure to take into account the age and individual psychological characteristics of children and adolescents in family upbringing	19.47	15.56	14.24	15, 38
6	Lack of involvement of the elderly in the upbringing of children in the family	6.86	6.02	4.20	5.31
7	Raising children alone in the family (single parenthood)	3, 70	4.09	5.42	4.24
8	Diminishing father's influence and role in the process of upbringing	2.74	3.62	4.26	3.46

9	Parents having behavior that is contrary to society's norms	12.4 3	1 3 , 2 4	1 4 , 2 1	13, 62
10	Inadequate financial and household conditions	9.2 8	9, 48	10.4 1	9.6 1

Therefore, it is desirable for parents, first of all, to have theoretical and practical knowledge of raising children in the family.

three-fourths of the parents of the young people living an unhealthy lifestyle, who participated in our study, stated that they did not read parenting articles in books, newspapers or magazines . It can be seen from this that parents ' lack of education knowledge, failure to use our national values, traditions and customs in the education process can lead to the violation of children's education, the emergence of various unhealthy behaviors and non-observance of a healthy lifestyle .

Also, according to the results of our research, the situation of "non-participation of the elderly in the upbringing of children" in the family has a negative effect on the upbringing of children . After all, it is not for nothing that our people say , " A house with a bee has a fairy . " Firstly, the fact that the elderly are almost at home leads to constant communication with children, to constantly monitor their activities, and secondly, it should not be forgotten that the abundance of life experience they have has an important place in children's upbringing.

It is known that our people have experienced the European way of life for many years. A few thousand years old traditions, customs, traditions and national education methods were replaced by the European culture of education. They were sometimes introduced through pressure. As a result, our nation lost its historically formed rich cultural and spiritual heritage, family upbringing methods.

has a negative impact on the effectiveness of education in Uzbek families today . As a result, the influential role of family education is decreasing, and the relationship between parents and children is becoming tense . Kindness, respect for children, and respect for adults are decreasing in families . This eventually began to affect the environment and society. That's probably why the behavior and behavior of young people on the streets sometimes makes people angry.

According to our observations, in families, specific ineffective methods are used in the relationship between parents and children. In particular, parents sometimes love their children too much. They cherish and honor them. They try not to infect them. They try to fulfill what they say or want. At first glance, you would say, what did the parents do? But such attitude of parents to children leads to the formation of negative feelings in children. As a result of this attitude shown by the parents, the child develops negative emotions such as arrogance, contempt for others, cunningness, lack of value for work, and impatience. Children with such feelings do not develop the feelings of hard work, nobility, respect and honoring others, appreciation of work, characteristic of the Uzbek people. They also have the habit of boasting, laughing at others, and pretending to be helpless. Children brought up in such a spirit have difficulties in thinking independently in problematic situations and coming to certain decisions. Such people are often isolated from their peers due to their inability to get along with their peers and the narrowness of their circle of friends.

our research, it was observed that such characteristics exist in families where young people live based on an unhealthy lifestyle . However , in addition to this , in such families, there is an unhealthy psychological environment, a fixed life goal and direction, a lack of respect and kindness among family members, a decrease in the level of educational influence of the family, the absence or decrease of the father's influence in the family, it was observed that there is no education of children based on national values and the lack of involvement of the elderly in the education of children in the family and the presence of a number of similar defects .

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